

Binomial Expansion with Optimized Combination of Combinatorics

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents innovative binomial expansions derived from the optimized combinations relating to the combinatorics. This binomial expansion will be useful for the researchers who are involving to solve the scientific problems.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: optimized combination, binomial coefficient, binomial expansion

I. Introduction to Optimized Combination

The optimized combination [1-2] applied on the iterative summation of mixed geometric series of same kind [3-9] is expressed as follows:

$$V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\cdots(r+n)}{n!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} = V_n^r,$$

$$i.e., \quad V_r^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{r+i}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!} = V_n^r \quad (n, r \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, r \in N),$$

where $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, V_r^n is a binomial coefficient, and $n!$ is the factorial of n .

Some results [1-6] of the optimized combination are provided below:

i). $V_n^0 = V_0^n = 1 \quad (n \geq 1 \text{ \& } n \in N),$

where V_n^0 always implies V_0^n , *i.e.*, $V_n^0 \Rightarrow V_0^n$.

Note that $V_r^n = V_n^r = (n+r)V_r = (n+r)V_n = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{r+i}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!}$ and $V_0^0 = 1$.

ii). $V_r^n = V_n^r \quad (n, r \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, r \in N) \text{ \& } V_n^0 = V_0^n \quad (n \geq 1 \text{ \& } n \in N).$

iii): $V_0^n + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n + \dots + V_r^n = V_r^{n+1} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^n = V_r^{n+1} \quad (n, r \in N).$

II. Novel Series of Optimized Combination

From the result (iii) in this paper, that is,

$1 + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n + \dots + V_r^n = V_r^{n+1} \Leftrightarrow 1 + V_n^1 + V_n^2 + V_n^3 + \dots + V_n^r = V_{n+1}^r$,
the following series and its summations are expressed:

$$(1). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)}{1!} = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n + (n+1) = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!}.$$

$$(2). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)}{2!} = 1 + 3 + 6 + \dots + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{3!}.$$

$$(3). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)}{3!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)}{4!}.$$

$$(4). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)(i+4)}{4!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)}{5!}.$$

Similarly, the series continues upto r times. The r^{th} series and its summation are:

$$(r). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)\dots(i+r)}{r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\dots(n+r)(n+r+1)}{(r+1)!}$$

$$i.e., \sum_{i=0}^n \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{i+j}{r!} = \prod_{i=1}^{r+1} \frac{n+i}{(r+1)!}$$

III. Conclusion

In this paper, the innovative binomial expansions have been derived using the results [1-6] of the optimized combination in the field of combinatorics. These binomial expansion will be useful for the researchers who are involving to solve the scientific problems and meet today's challenges [4].

IV. References

- [1] Annamalai C (2020) "Combinatorial Technique for Optimizing the combination", The Journal of Engineering and Exact Sciences – jCEC, Vol. 6(2), pp 0189-0192.

- [2] Annamalai C (2019) “A Model of Iterative Computations for Recursive Summability”, *Tamsui Oxford Journal of Information and Mathematical Sciences – Airiti Library*, Vol. 33(1), pp 75-77.
- [3] Annamalai C (2018) “Annamalai’s Computing Model for Algorithmic Geometric Series and its Mathematical Structures”, *Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, Vol. 3(1), PP 1-6.
- [4] Annamalai C (2010) “Applications of Exponential Decay and Geometric Series in Effective Medicine”, *Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology*, Vol.1 (1), pp 51-54.
- [5] Annamalai C (2009, “A Novel Computational Technique for the Geometric Progression of Powers of Two”, *Journal of Scientific and Mathematical Research*, Vol. 3, pp 16-17.
- [6] Annamalai C (2020) “Novel Computing Technique in combinatorics, Archive ouverte HAL. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02862222>.
- [7] Annamalai C (2020) “Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics, Archive ouverte HAL. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02865835>.
- [8] Annamalai C (2022) “Combinatorial Relation of Optimized Combination with Permutation”, OSF Preprints,. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ymk8b>.
- [9] Annamalai C (2022) .” Novel Binomial Series and its Summations”, *Authorea*. DOI: 10.22541/au.164933885.53684288.